

Demystifying and Democratizing Early Childhood Music Education through MOOCs: Enhancing Cognitive Development through Empowering Educators

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Abstract. The Smart Start for Early Childhood Education Centers program by the RCM is a research-backed early learning music program developed by a neuroscientist and empowers early childhood educators to foster cognitive development in young children through music-making, regardless of the educator's musical ability. Through rigorous research, we have designed a MOOC, accredited by IACET, that equips teachers with essential knowledge and tools to integrate music-making into their classrooms in a meaningful, effective, and fun way. By providing accessible training and professional development to teachers through a MOOC, this innovative approach scales early childhood music education, democratizing access to its developmental benefits.

Keywords: Early Education, Music Education, Professional Development.

1 Introduction

Most children spend on average between 15-35 hours per week in early childhood education (ECE) centers (Rey-Guerra et al., 2023). With children spending so much time in ECE centers, these centers and their teachers have a profound influence on how children develop cognitively, socially, and emotionally, (Burchinal et al., 2015). We also know that access to early music education has a profound effect on childhood development as well, including language development, emotional regulation, and executive functioning (Gerry, Unrau, & Trainor, 2012; Hutchins, 2018). Although music education has been found to have positive effects on early childhood development, many ECE teachers feel ill-equipped to deliver formal music education due to their lack of musical training or ability (Kirby et al., 2023). Additionally, access to quality music education for children is scarce in more rural areas (Henley & Barton 2022) as well as areas with lower socio-economic status (Dansereau, Donahue, & Speelman, 2024).

Based on these findings, our goal at the Royal Conservatory of Music was to create a rigorous online course specifically for early childhood teachers to empower them to teach the RCM's Smart Start music curriculum designed for children aged birth through 6-years-old. Our hope was by offering accessible music training to teachers in the form of a MOOC, we may positively influence the accessibility of music education to underserved communities.

2 ECE Teachers and Music Education Training

2.1 The Effect of Professional Development on Teaching Practice

Effective professional development for ECE teachers results in significant improvements in their teaching practice including greater sensitivity and attachment to their children and improved disposition towards developmentally appropriate instruction (Matthews et al., 2000), as well as a more positive attitude (Naber, 1995). This positive impact on the teacher's practice has a positive impact on their children's development. Research suggests that children demonstrate higher-level skills when their teachers receive training, including more developed language, motor, and cognitive skills (Bowman et al., 2001; Myers, 2006).

2.2 ECE Teachers and Music Education

In a 2023 study by Kirby, Dahbi, Surrain, et al., two groups of ECE teachers were interviewed in a focus group setting to better understand their relationship with music in the classroom. The results showed that most of the teachers reported a lack of confidence in at least some of their musical abilities, however, despite their lack of comfort, 95.8% use music in their classroom in some way. The teachers also expressed a desire for more resources to be able to offer more robust music curricula in their classrooms.

Many ECE teachers, however, feel ill-equipped to teach music curricula within their classrooms citing a lack of training (Rajan, 2017b). Furthermore, studies have shown that ECE teachers are dissatisfied with the music education courses that do exist, citing a lack of practical application and overly theoretical curriculum (Koutsoupidou, 2010).

3 Music Education and Young Children

The effects of music on childhood development have been well-documented with research studies citing increased cognitive, language, and literacy skills (Hutchins 2018; Linnavalli et al., 2018), increased fine motor skills (Schlaug et al., 2005), and improved social-emotional regulation (Schellenberg et al., 2015).

The accessibility of music education is a little-researched topic, however, a body of evidence suggests that children who enjoy greater access to music education generally live in or have easy access to more urban areas where resources are more available (Henley & Barton, 2022). In ECE centers, access to quality music education has been found to be dependent on the wealth of the center, with more affluent centers offering higher-quality and more frequent music education than their less-affluent counterparts (Dansereau, Donahue, & Speelman, 2024).

4 MOOC Design and Structure

To address issues set forth in this paper, namely the accessibility of high-quality music education for teachers and access to music education for children, the Royal Conservatory of Music developed a 4-week MOOC for teachers to encourage and empower them to offer the Royal Conservatory's Smart Start early childhood music curriculum in their communities and schools. In developing an effective online MOOC for teachers, we relied on a body of research findings (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017; Baran, Correia, & Thompson, 2011), and feedback received after running pilot sessions.

The final design of the course is a 4-week, online course authored by the founders and developers of Smart Start that ran once a month from May 2023 through January 2025. The course consists of asynchronous video content, readings, including scientific research papers, demonstrations, discussion questions, and weekly synchronous video sessions with breakout rooms and study groups facilitated by expert Smart Start teachers. The course includes multiple formative assessments throughout, offering immediate feedback, as well as summative assessments, requiring students to demonstrate their understanding. Students complete self-evaluations and receive feedback on their work from a Smart Start certified teacher as well as from their peers. The MOOC is accredited by International Accreditors for Continuing Education and Training (IACET), ensuring the teachers receive recognized PD credits (CEUs) upon completion.

5 Methods

5.1 Participants

Our sample size consisted of 238 educators from 45 schools (19 located throughout the US and 26 located throughout Canada) who completed the course between May 2023 and January 2025. Teachers across the US and Canada were made aware of the course through RCM email campaigns and social media ads on Facebook and Instagram. Of the 238 educators, 101 completed the questionnaire at the end of course completion.

5.2 Measures

The educators were assessed by school geographic classification, socio-economic status associated with school location based on median household income, general course satisfaction, and whether the teachers felt equipped to teach the Smart Start curriculum after the course.

To measure school location, geographic classification, and socio-economic status of the school municipality, teachers were asked to submit the address of their associated school. Since we were working with data from two different countries (the US and Canada) and both countries record economic data differently, we separated the data out and looked at each country separately. Using US and Canadian census data (U.S. Census Bureau, n.d., Statistics Canada, 2021) we were able to ascertain the median household income of the school's associated municipality. We used data for US income

categorizations from the Federal Reserve Economic Database (Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis, n.d.) and from Spring Financial (Spring Financial, 2024) to establish Canadian income categorizations. We used the National Center for Education Statistics' Locale Classifications and Criteria to identify schools' geographic classification in the US and Statistics Canada to identify schools' geographic classification in Canada.

To measure the teachers' course satisfaction and confidence in teaching the Smart Start curriculum, teachers were asked to complete a short course-completion questionnaire after successfully completing the course. The questions utilized a Likert scale of either 1-5 or 1-4 depending on the question and asked participants to the degree to which they agreed or disagreed with specific statements. The questionnaire also included a free response section. The questionnaire is available at the end of the online course as a Microsoft Form. Over the course of two weeks, two announcement prompts are made in the course to inform participants of the questionnaire. The questionnaire closes three days after final grading has been completed.

6 Results

6.1 Socio-Economic Status and Geographic Classification

In assessing the socio-economic status of the municipalities where the 19 schools were located throughout the US, we found 2 of the 19 (10.5%) fell within the "Lower Income" bracket, 16 of the 19 (84.2%) schools fell within the "Middle Income" bracket, and 1 of the 19 schools (5.3%) fell within the "Upper Income" bracket, see Table 1.

Table 1. Schools by US Income (in USD)

Lower Income (Below \$56,600)	Middle Income (\$56,600-\$169,800)	Upper Income (Above \$169,800)
2	16	1

Upon further analysis of overall US median income trends, we discovered 6 of the 19 schools (31.6%) in the US are within municipalities with median incomes below the overall US median income of \$80,610 (Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis, n.d.).

In assessing the socio-economic status of the municipalities where the 26 schools were located throughout Canada, we found 1 of the 26 (3.9%) fell within the "Lower Income" bracket, 20 of the 26 (76.9%) schools fell within the "Middle Income" bracket, 5 of the 26 (19.2%) schools fell within the "Upper-Middle Income" bracket, and 0 of the 26 (0.0%) schools fell within the "Upper Income" bracket, see Table 2.

Table 2. Schools by Canadian Income (in CAD)

Lower Income (Below \$53,359)	Middle Income (\$53,359-\$106,717)	Upper-Middle Income (\$106,717- \$235,675)	Upper Income (Above \$235,675)

Upon further analysis of overall Canadian average income trends, we discovered 5 of the 26 schools (19.2%) in Canada are within municipalities with average incomes below the overall Canadian average income of \$70,000 (Spring Financial, 2024).

In assessing the geographic classification of the 19 schools that were located throughout the US, we found 2 of the 19 (10.5%) schools fell within the “Town-Remote” classification. 3 of the 19 (15.8%) schools fell within the “Town-Distant” classification. 1 of the 19 (5.3%) schools fell within the “Town-Fringe” classification. 2 of the 19 (10.5%) schools fall within the “Suburban-Small” classification. 3 of the 19 (15.8%) schools fell within the “Suburban-Mid” classification. 1 of the 19 (5.3%) schools were in the “City-Small” classification, 2 of the 19 (10.5%) schools were in the “City-Mid” classification, and 5 of the 19 (26.3%) schools were in the “City-Large” classification, see Table 3.

Table 3. US Schools Geographic Classification

Town – Remote	Town - Distant	Town - Fringe	Suburban-Small	Suburban - Mid	City-Small	City - Mid	City - Large
2	3	1	2	3	1	2	5

31.6% of the schools in the US are in a town geographically classified as remote, distant, or fringe while 26.3% are in cities with populations larger than 250,000.

In assessing the geographic classification of the 26 schools that were located throughout Canada, we found 3 of the 26 (11.5%) fell within the “Small-Rural” classification. 1 of the 26 (3.9%) schools fell within the “Fringe” classification. 3 of the 26 (11.5%) schools fell within the “Small” classification. 4 of the 26 (15.4%) schools fell within the “Medium” classification. 15 of the 26 (57.7%) schools were in the “Large” classification, see Table 4.

Table 4. Canadian Schools Geographic Classification

Small-Rural	Fringe	Small	Medium	Large
3	1	3	4	15

26.9% of the schools in Canada are in towns geographically classified as small-rural, fringe, or small while 57.7% are in cities with populations larger than 100,000.

6.2 Course Questionnaire

Of the 101 questionnaire participants, when asked how satisfied they were with the course, 96.0% of respondents reported being satisfied with the course to some degree, see Table 5.

Table 5. Teacher Satisfaction

Very Satisfied	Satisfied	Somewhat Satisfied	Somewhat Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied
48.5%	35.4%	12.1%	2%	2%

When asked to rate the level to which they agreed with the statement “I feel confident in my understanding of the Smart Start lesson plans and activity structure, 75.0% Agreed, 21.0% Somewhat Agreed, 4.0% Somewhat Disagreed, and 0.0% Disagreed, see Table 6.

When asked to rate the level to which they agreed with the statement “I understand the pedagogical methodology of the Smart Start Curriculum,” 87.0% Agreed, 11.0% Somewhat Agreed, 2.0% Somewhat Disagreed, and 0.0% Disagreed, see Table 6.

Table 6. Teacher Confidence and Understanding of Course Curriculum

	Agree	Somewhat Agree	Somewhat Disagree	Disagree
Teacher Confidence in Understanding	73%	24%	3%	0%
Teacher Understanding: Lesson Plans and Activities	75%	21%	4%	0%
Teacher Understanding: Pedagogical Methodology	87%	11%	2%	0%

At the end of the questionnaire, write in responses included “This was a great course, I’m excited to use more of it in my practice!”, “This course was so insightful and has already made me reorganize my [teaching].”, “Excited to start offering the classes!”, and “Thank you for this opportunity. I look forward to bringing the Smart Start program to our community in the near future.”

Respondents also suggested many opportunities for improvement, including additional lesson plan reviews, extended Q&A sessions with the course instructor, and additional classroom management strategies. The most common write-in was from 17.8% of respondents requesting additional full class recordings and/or opportunities to participate in in-person practicum exercises.

7 Discussion

This study aimed to explore the effectiveness of a Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) designed to empower educators with the knowledge and skills to integrate the Smart Start early childhood music curriculum, thereby enhancing cognitive development in young children through music. The results from the course participants provided insight into how this innovative approach may contribute to improving early

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childhood music education and expand access to high-quality resources for educators in various geographic classifications and socio-economic contexts.

A key component of this study was the exploration of the geographic classification and socio-economic factors influencing the access to and quality of music education for young children. The findings showed that while most of the schools associated with the participating educators were in middle-income areas in the US and Canada, 31.6% of the schools in the US were in areas with median incomes below the national median and 19.2% of the schools in Canada were in areas with an average income less than the national average. This outcome suggests the course was more successful in reaching educators in lower-income areas in the US than in Canada. This result is encouraging, as it indicates that the course may help provide access to music education in economically disadvantaged areas, however, further investigation is needed to understand how socio-economic factors might influence educators' ability to apply what they have learned in practice, as financial constraints can impact the availability of necessary classroom materials and resources.

When assessing geographic classification, the findings showed 31.6% of the schools in the US were in towns geographically classified as remote, distant, or fringe while 26.3% were in cities with populations larger than 250,000. In Canada, 26.9% of the schools were in towns geographically classified as Small-rural, fringe, or small while 57.7% were in cities with populations larger than 100,000. This data suggests that while the course was successful in reaching more rural educators in the US, it was less successful in Canada. Previous research has demonstrated that children in low-income or rural areas have less access to music education (Henley & Barton, 2022). While the MOOC model holds potential to bridge this gap, there remains an opportunity to improve outreach strategies to target schools in these underserved areas more effectively.

One of the main outcomes of this study was identifying the positive response from educators regarding the effectiveness of the course in building their confidence in understanding the Smart Start curriculum. Most participants reported high satisfaction with the course, with 48.5% of respondents indicating they were "Very Satisfied." This suggests that the MOOC design effectively met its goals of providing educators with the necessary tools and confidence to teach music in their classrooms.

Additionally, the results indicated that educators felt confident in their understanding of the Smart Start lesson plans and activities. This is an important finding, as many ECE teachers have expressed feelings of inadequacy in teaching music (Kirby et al., 2023; Rajan, 2017b).

The impact of the course was also evident in the participants' readiness to implement the Smart Start curriculum in their classrooms. Many respondents expressed enthusiasm about applying the program to their teaching practice, with several mentioning that they had already begun reorganizing their lessons to incorporate music. This highlights the potential of MOOCs to scale professional development in ways that can create a broad, lasting impact across diverse regions, including those that traditionally lack access to quality in-person training opportunities. Furthermore, this feedback points to the power of an accessible, online learning platform to democratize access to early childhood music education for teachers in rural or under-resourced areas, which may otherwise face barriers to obtaining in-depth music training (Henley & Barton, 2022).

Several areas for improvement were identified through the course questionnaire. Many respondents suggested additional opportunities for practice, such as full-class recordings or participatory practicum exercises. This feedback highlights the desire for more hands-on, practical application of the content. Providing more opportunities for teachers to engage in interactive and immersive learning experiences could help strengthen the course and improve its overall impact.

8 Conclusion and Next Steps

The current results indicate that our MOOC was somewhat successful at democratizing music education in low- to mid-level income areas, especially in the US. While the course did reach some teachers in more rural areas, more outreach to rural educators specifically is needed. The results also indicate that we achieved our goal of demystifying music education, with the large majority of teachers enrolled reporting a high level of satisfaction and confidence in their ability to understand and teach the Smart Start curriculum.

The constructive feedback provided in the questionnaire has been used to add additional time for discussion and practice with the instructor. This feedback also forms the foundation for programming within a continuing education portal developed by the RCM for teachers, where monthly live events and on-demand webinar recordings are available to teachers. We have also developed a shorter, completely asynchronous version of the course to increase access. This course represents a step forward in democratizing and demystifying music education and its cognitive benefits.

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